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Data Review

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Abstract

The Tajikistan Household Panel Survey examines migration, remittance behavior, and labor market participation at the household level. Conducted in 2011, it builds on earlier surveys from 2007 and 2009 by re-interviewing the same households, creating a panel dataset, allowing for longitudinal analysis. The survey covers over 1,500 households across Tajikistan and includes detailed information on their members' demographics, employment, income, and migration histories (primarily to Russia). Access to the dataset is restricted and requires a formal application (see the review).

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Review of the Tajikistan Household Panel Survey by Stas Gorelik

The Tajikistan Household Panel Survey aims to examine migration, remittance behavior, and patterns of labor market participation across households (the unit of analysis) in Tajikistan. The study was implemented in 2011 by the Institute for East and Southeast European Studies (Regensburg), in cooperation with the SHARQ Research Center (Dushanbe), which conducted the survey on the ground. The project was part of the broader study “Migration and Remittances in Central Asia: The Case of Kazakhstan and Tajikistan,” funded by the Volkswagen Foundation.

The survey builds on the design and findings of the Living Standards Measurement Surveys conducted in Tajikistan in 2007 and 2009 by the World Bank and UNICEF. The 2011 wave was designed to re-interview at least some households that had participated in these earlier surveys, thereby creating a panel dataset suitable for longitudinal research on migration behavior, labor market participation, and household welfare. Accordingly, the 2011 study should be understood as a follow-up wave, relying on the household lists from the 2007 and 2009 surveys.

Data collection took place in late 2011. The dataset includes interviews with more than 1,500 households, comprising 9,608 household members across Tajikistan’s five main administrative regions. Interviews were conducted face-to-face, primarily in Tajik.

In terms of content, the questionnaire covers both individual- and household-level characteristics. It records demographic information, education, and labor market participation. A substantial portion of the survey focuses on migration-related issues, including respondents’ migration histories (primarily to Russia), employment conditions abroad, and patterns of remittance behavior. In addition, the survey collects data on income sources and consumption expenditures.

Details on the survey’s implementation and key findings are available in a report at the following link: https://leibniz-ios.de/fileadmin/mediamanager/002_forschung/02_dokumente/Booklet-TI-web.pdf.

At least two limitations should be noted. First, because the survey relies on re-interviewing households from earlier waves, panel attrition is unavoidable, as in similar studies. Second, some information—including migration experiences and remittance flows—is self-reported and may therefore be subject to recall error and other biases, including social desirability bias. Access to the dataset is restricted. Researchers must request access through IOS Regensburg’s LaMBDa research data repository by submitting a description of their research project along with other required information (e.g., institutional affiliation).